

Sequence recovery

0.00 0.25 0.50 0.75 1.00

Trigonospora zeylanica
Trigonospora obtusiloba
Strophocaulon unitum Fiji
Sphaerostephanos hochreutineri
Sphaerostephanos hirtisora
Sphaerostephanos elatus
Sphaerostephanos ataspirii
Rehottumia truncata
Rehottumia magnifica 10556
Pseudocyclosorus tyloides
Pseudocyclosorus tyloides Tuberculifer
Pseudocyclosorus subochthodes
Pseudocyclosorus repens
Pseudocyclosorus pulcher
Pseudocyclosorus ornatus
Pseudocyclosorus falcilobus
Pseudocyclosorus esquirolii Taiwan
Pseudocyclosorus esquirolii Sichuan
Pseudocyclosorus cf. esquirolii Vietnam
Pseudocyclosorus Comores
Pronephrium fidelei
Pronephrium affine
Pneumatopteris Darksii
Pneumatopteris humbertii
Pneumatopteris affra
Plesioneuron keysserianum
Plesioneuron imbricatum 3623
Pelazoneuron tuerckheimii
Pelazoneuron schizotis
Pelazoneuron puberulum Mexico
Pelazoneuron puberulum California
Pelazoneuron patens dissimilis
Pelazoneuron patens
Pelazoneuron ovatum lindheimeri
Pelazoneuron ovatum
Pelazoneuron kunthii
Pelazoneuron depilatum
Pelazoneuron clavale
Pelazoneuron berroi
Pelazoneuron augescens
Pelazoneuron albicaule X puberulum
Pelazoneuron albicaule
Pelazoneuron abruptum
Pakau pennigera
Mesopteris Tonkinensis
Menisorus pauciflorus Cameroon
Menisciopsis wallele
Menisciopsis rubrinervis
Menisciopsis rubida
Menisciopsis penangiana
Menisciopsis lakhimpurensis
Menisciopsis cyatheoides Wood
Menisciopsis cyatheoides Fawcett
Menisciopsis boydiae
Grypothrix simplex
Grypothrix salicifolia
Grypothrix rubicunda
Glaphyopteridopsis emeiensis
Christella xpalmeri
Christella xintermedia
Christella subpubescens Vietnam
Christella subpubescens Sulawesi
Christella sp. Sichuan
Christella sp. Philippines
Christella siamensis
Christella parasitica
Christella papilio
Christella latipinna
Christella jaculosa Philippines
Christella jaculosa Hunan
Christella hispidula versicolor
Christella hispidula repens
Christella hispidula inconstans
Christella hispidula Mexico
Christella hispidula Java
Christella hispidula Ethiopia
Christella hispidula Bolivia
Christella harveyi
Christella guentziana
Christella guamensis
Christella gretheri
Christella evoluta
Christella ensifer
Christella dentata
Christella conspersa
Christella chaseana
Christella calvescens
Christella calcarea
Christella acuminata
Chingia fijiensis
Amblovenatum opulentum Vietnam
Amblovenatum opulentum Costa Rica
Amblovenatum immersum
Abacopteris repanda
Abacopteris nitida
Abacopteris gymnopteridifrons
Abacopteris birii
Abacopteris aspera
Abacopteris aff. peitochlamys

Locus

